

THE ROLE OF PHYSICS TEACHING AND SCHOOL TEXTBOOKS TO IMPROVE ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH STUDENTS

VASILEIOS AG. DROUGAS¹

¹University of Ioannina Greece,
Greek Ministry of Education and Religious Affairs,
ADAMAS University India

ABSTRACT

Today in the school there is a change in the thinking of the students towards Physics Science. This may be due to the materials chosen in the school timetable in the textbooks, the lack of laboratories and the way physics is taught in public schools. It is important to find a method to change the way students think through innovative learning programs and innovative teaching. Students are tired of the many subjects and the way Science is taught in public schools today. It is also important that there should again be a change in the desire of students to pursue physical science, and for this purpose, basic textbooks need to be written and there should be substantial cooperation with university professors. In this study, a proposal for the study and presentation of Physical Science with applications to the human body, medicine and everyday life is presented and solutions are proposed with the aim of changing the way of thinking of students and teachers.

Key words: Physics, Textbooks, Students, Physics Applications

Introduction

In recent years, research and studies in the teaching of Physics have changed the data in teaching as well as in the presentation of physics topics, especially at the secondary education level.

This was agreed to by the upgrading of the physics equipment, modern teaching ideas related to the students' research and also by the change of style in the school textbooks.

However, the correlation between teaching and learning materials seems to fall significantly short of the goal. This happens in secondary schools in Greece mainly due to the large number of different subjects and the amount of equipment in the limited time of the school year.

Especially in physics, this seems to be connected to the diversity of the chapters, the lack of experiments as well as language problems and the lack of connection between the theory and its applications.

Contributing to this lag is the lack of writing standards with clear teaching definitions and certainly the lack of teachers who would approach the students more.

Although the research in the teaching of physics and the approaches they recommend to the students are very great,, in recent years there has been an inability of students to approach

physics as smoothly as we expected, something that seems to continue in the physics departments as well.

School textbooks have a large share of this inadequacy, since they do not clearly show the applications of physical science to society and its contribution to many other sciences.

There is therefore an important issue today in Greece regarding school textbooks. Can they convince students of their adequacy, usefulness, usability, and provide direction-finding impulses to students?

Although students experience physics every day through the most perfect experimental laboratory at their disposal, the human body, they do not seem to understand the utility of physics in it.

The significant rise of the biological sciences in recent years in both research and student preferences as prospective students has helped to create new scientific fields of research and study, theories, experimentation, and researcher jobs that might not have been easily imagined before. For twenty years, (Gayton 1984)

All the preparatory work to form a first, but important view of physics is in high school classes. Especially when the positive sciences are currently in such a great upsurge, it is very important that students are properly informed before deciding on the direction of their studies.

The applications of physics to humans are very many and multiply as the fields of study in the various sciences multiply today and also as the mechanisms of the human body are discovered (Drougas V. (c). 2005)

School textbooks have the potential either directly or indirectly to provide such stimuli and direct students to find the right path that suits them.

Great emphasis must be placed on the simple and everyday application of the sciences that children are taught at school, because this will highlight their real interests.

Physical science began to be organized in laboratories from the time of Newton and Galileo and through experiential observation.

Physicists learned to use simple and more complex instruments to measure and correlate data to draw conclusions.

Today, experiments are done in a modern environment with complex instruments related to the development of electronics and IT. However, the observation of simple phenomena in order to form physical knowledge is done in the same way and this remains an important and life-saving step for the dissemination of natural science and the initiation of children to it.

Experiential experiments always arouse the interest of children and can improve their perceptual ability, which plays an important role in the development of critical and creative thinking but also in introducing them to the mentality and art of the experimenter.

The human body is a real laboratory with which students come into daily contact as they unconsciously or consciously experiment with it and experience the conclusions of this observation.

This happens in play, in simple motor experiences, in physical training and in their various hobbies and in everyday observation.

If students understand the true value of this lab, then they will be able to experience physics and draw or compare conclusions that most of the time textbooks either describe poorly or don't approach at all.

This research study within the postgraduate study program of the Physics Department of the University of Ioannina aims to highlight the creative presence of physical science in the human body and to activate children's imagination about the human body with data.

At the same time, to indicate ways of introducing relevant passages in school textbooks in order to effectively inform students both in dealing with specific issues of into theory and about its applications in everyday life.

This will help children to choose correctly in the direction they will follow and orient themselves in their future choice in relation to natural science, whose presence is important but also evident in many branches of science.

Such are medicine, physiology, biomechanics, biology, astronomy, archeology, engineering, electrical and mechanical engineering, mathematics etc.

An important approach is attempted to the problem of introducing concepts of physics in various directions in the school textbooks of the unified High School with the aim of activating the students towards the search for the applications of physical science in modern reality.

Also, in the creation of proposals and models for the transformation of physics textbooks into real tools for the search, for applications and knowledge in the future development of students and in the search for the directions they could follow.

Students will have the opportunity to search for the real applications of physics, which, in this case, is directed towards the human body, related to the modern human sciences, medicine, biology and physiology (Drougas V. Doctoral Dissertation, Medical School, University of Ioannina, 2006), as well as with sports which is an important current in the modern era.

The experimental part of the research was made up of students of B and C of the unified high schools and is based on the analysis of the data of the research done with the method of completing a questionnaire from primary, material, i.e. answers and criticisms, of the students themselves in their place of education - inside the school something that is very important to explore their point of view and their thoughts.

The study of the answers and the resulting data was done with statistical analysis through the statistical package SPSS-15, which can give us combined approaches of the questions and the answers of the respondents of the sample in each case.

The sample consisted of students in urban (cities) and rural high schools.

Areas (villages)

With this investigation, we have the possibility to approach the views and demands of the students by region depending on the direction they are following in terms of their requirements for information and presentation of the physics subjects in the school textbooks in which they are examined and, much more, they highlight the directions in physical science.

The study of various similar approaches would be important and could be studied and explored in other relevant research by students, so that the textbook is not a simple informational book of theory and application study with mathematical formulas and pre-

planned exercises in physics, but also a comprehensive guide for students in orienting themselves and restoring their confidence in physics.

The role of Physics in school today

Physics today is one of the most applied sciences in modern technology and research. It is science that enables the scholar to combine laws, rules and predictions based on a group of distinguished theories and results from experiments.

Physics is one of the important subjects in B and C high school and a compulsory subject that is considered in the Pan-Hellenic exams for positive and technological direction.

The general education course in high school B is a compulsory core course for all three majors. However, the physics course of general education in high school is optional and can be attended by students from all three directions.

Although physics remains in an almost stable position in terms of the quality of the knowledge it offers and in terms of its contribution to new application technologies, it is nevertheless considered a difficult subject by students.

This is probably due to the presentation of physics materials from high school and the first grade of the Lyceum.

The children, as we can see in the conclusions from the statistical presentation of the responses of this research, seek to document physics and its laws in their daily life and experience. They are not satisfied with vague theories and data that may not have any real meaning for them, or at least they cannot recognize their meaning (Drougas V. 2008).

Although physics can provide answers and solutions to many questions that could arise from the study of other sciences, it is probably not given in the right way to students through school textbooks and perhaps even by the teachers themselves, as this particular case shows.

Children seem to read physics to understand the basics of the theory if that is finally done and much more to learn the mechanics of solving a certain set of exercises to pass the exam.

So we cannot say whether physics in today's school has finally taken its true place or whether it retains its scientific connotation. However, in recent years, students probably show some relative aversion, something that may be due to the excessive spread of new technologies and certainly IT

In the present research, a relevant investigation is attempted for the applications of physics in the human body, which is an important criterion for the choice of students' direction towards medical and biological sciences.

It is important that students understand and have an informed view on the applications of physics (Drougas V. 2002). This will help them not only to correctly choose the direction they will follow but also to explore the areas they would like to deal with, in possible research of theirs.

The role of textbooks in the learning process

School textbooks have a somewhat important role and goal and are samples on which students' knowledge can be seamlessly and formally based during the learning process at school.

Although this is commonly accepted, in previous years, no solutions and proposals were sought that would aim at the best possible approach to high school textbooks in accordance with modern teaching trends, which come from modern education systems and include applications from modern research into didactic physics.

School textbooks should be designed to promote knowledge and its dissemination, to coordinate the efforts of students in order not to get lost in the abundance of data, and to be a real ally of students in their daily adaptation and assimilation of knowledge. (Driver R., Squires A., Rushworth P., Wood-Robinson V (2000))

In recent years, the school textbooks in Greece have been significantly upgraded and the abundance of research and conclusions in the teaching of the various sciences and, in this case, Physical science has probably contributed to this.

However, they still lag far behind, and this is also contributed to by the multitude of different and unrelated courses on the syllabus that seem anything but likely to help the student.

Physics as well as mathematics and, in recent years, biology also play an important role in the formation of standards of knowledge today in the modern school.

Scientific intervention was attempted with modern funds and with applications that could help high school students. However, this did not become reality, as can be seen from the choice of the physics general education course by the G high school candidates.

Although the textbook on the respective courses provides important information and references to sources and applications to man and to various daily problems, it nevertheless failed to win over the candidates who seemed not to declare the physics course as a large percentage as in the previous years.

So the role of school physics textbooks, especially in the last grades of high school, is:

To activate the students

To form a positive climate towards natural sciences

To help the student understand and, of course, assimilate important concepts of physics and its applications

To give directions to the student by searching for interests through the courses

To provide significant help to the material with direct access to it, both in theory and in problems

To activate students towards physics

To provide immediate answers to questions and issues that concern students about the immediate environment they experience every day

Finally, to be an integrated language and knowledge tool that will help students feel safe.

The school textbook is therefore a multi-tool that takes students on a journey to physics and knowledge through texts, observations, applications, experimental data, searches and exploratory knowledge that activates thought and documents truth and covers students' interests to the extent that this can be achieved within the framework of a school year.

The school textbook is not the infallible and unique book that remains unchanged over time but is improved, transformed according to the needs of the syllabus and the requirements of the students it is going to serve.

So it requires continuous monitoring of students' interests, the development of science and the adaptation of physics to new data (Drougas V. 2003).

In this way, comprehensive knowledge is created, contributing substantially to the future course of the students and to their activation in science matters.

Learning standards in the textbooks of the unified high school

One of the basic questions that one could ask the initiators and creators of modern school textbooks in Greece is what is the role and learning patterns that the new books tend to create.

How easily students can adapt to modern standards, keeping up even more with the rapid development of modern technology and the abundance of information provided.

Students, more than any other era, seem to show an aversion to the textbook and this is the main reason why they probably get angry with it, and as a result, most of the time they destroy it, draw colorful shapes on it, or throw it away or give it up. At a random point. (Whitaker, P. (χ.χ.)).

It is a fact that the school textbooks that resulted from the upgrading of education in Greece introduced important innovative ideas that, probably the students in turn seem to assimilate them easily, but perhaps they have not understood their importance as much as happened with the introduction of images for more complete understanding of the theory (Drougas V. (2004))

School textbooks tend to use knowledge of physics through a kind of discussion with the subject, with figures, diagrams and reference development and closed or open-ended probing questions and problems.

References to inserts in the margins of books have been increasing in recent years and this seems to help students digest the material and understand the implications of physics, which the majority of students do by comparing theory and inserts reports and observations. (Kolb, D. (1984)).

As long as this is done by prompting the teachers as a form of valid opinion and view on how to study.

In general, the textbooks of the unified lyceum attempt

Restructuring of existing materials

Effort for a more effective approach and presentation of each chapter

Possibility of a better relationship of the student with theory and mathematical typology

More effective management of knowledge in a small amount of information so that the book is accessible to students

Presentation of sources and quotations alongside the development of the theory

References to applications and data that could potentially activate the student

Language improvement and cultivation

Correlation of physics with other sciences and references

Creating a climate of trust towards the book on the part of teachers and students

Conclusions

It is very important to gather data from various branches of applied physics and create a very important textbook that will cover thoroughly the applications of physics. The student will be able to draw information from this textbook, perhaps even as a supplement to the main physics textbook he will have in his school.

Solutions should be invented for the more analytical approach of the prospective students of physics departments that will be born from a more complete understanding of physical science within the school and from an even greater understanding of the applications and directions that physics can give today to the wider research and technological field of applications.

It is very important not only in the philosophy and strict principles of a really complex physical science, but to convince children that physics is well hidden but also manifests itself every day in the simplest processes of our experience in the immediate environment in which we grow.

Physics is a simple thought process of understanding what is happening around us and what we are a part of. So we live with nature every moment, we play with it, we wonder about it, and we create plans through the reality and imagination we live. Only then do we understand it and experience the conditions under which it works and reveal its secrets to us. (Drougas V. (2009))

REFERENCES

- Driver R., Squires A., Rushworth P., Wood-Robinson V., Building science concepts, a global compendium of student ideas, Ed. Print it, Αθήνα, 2000
- Drougas V. Doctoral Dissertation School of Medicine Univ. of Ioannina 2006
- Drougas V. Diagrammatic Representation of Physical Quantities of Kinematics in the 2nd High School Textbook and Students' Comprehension Problems, 2nd International Educational Conference March 14-15-16 Arta 2008
- Drougas V.: Factors Affecting Kinetic Equilibrium in Classical Physical Mechanics. 1st International Convention of Classical Sports, Trikala November 1 – 3, 2002.
- Drougas V. (c): Physical and motor effects on humans from the modern environment, Pan-Hellenic training conference INEP-EKDD Nafplion 19-21 Sept. 2003
- Drougas V. : Reference of applications to the human body in the Physics textbooks of the three classes of the unified Lyceum, 10th Panhellenic Conference of Physics EEF, Loutraki 29 Jan-1 Feb. 2004
- Drougas V. The contribution of virtual reality to the study of science courses at school 2nd EEEP-DTPE Conference October 15-16, 2005 Athens
- Drougas V.: I play and learn Physics, D. Publications 2009
- Gayton: Human physiology, Litsas Publications Athens 1984
- Kolb, D. (1984). *Experiential Learning*. New Jersey: Pentice Hall.
- Whitaker, P. (χ.χ.). *Managing to Learn. Aspects of Reflective and Experiential Learning in Schools*. Cassell.159